

Deep Neural Networks based Optical Character Recognition for Parking Signs

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Abstract

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a common computer recognition technology that is used to extract textual information from an image or document. OCR technologies often detect and extract the text contained in images and make it computer-readable. As shown in many previous studies, text written images do not always have good quality to be recognized by automatic OCR systems. This study compares the performance of automatic OCR systems such as Google and Amazon on the parking sign OCR dataset that we have prepared. In addition, it is proved that a system developed as a result of deep research on the latest technologies can give more efficient and high accuracy results.

Keywords: Optical Character Recognition, Text Detection, Text Recognition, Convolutional Neural Network, Recurrent Neural Network

1. Introduction

Extracting textual information from natural images is an important issue that has recently attracted attention in the computer vision field and many studies[1; 2; 3; 4] have addressed the topic. Although work in this area has achieved great success, this subject is still challenging due to the long text sentences, poor photo quality and complicated background.

Recently, Optic Character Recognition models based on the deep learning method[5; 6; 7; 8; 2]

have shown promising performances. Most of these models handle and solve the problem as two separate tasks, text detection and text recognition[9; 4].

The aim of this paper to compare the performance of these models based on deep learning methods. To achieve this goal, a dataset of parking signs was prepared first and then the state-of-the-art technology was investigated in depth. A high precision system has been developed to recognize parking sign images.

This work offers the possibility to create a better custom OCR system based on final detection and independent recognition models.

2. Related Work

Text detection and recognition is an active topic in the fields of computer vision and document analysis. In this section, a close examination and analysis of some methods will be presented.

2.1. Text Detection

Distinguishing text from natural images is one of the hot topics that computer vision field has focused on in recent years. Many important papers have been published on this subject in recent years[10; 11; 9].

Usually the models proposed in these papers are compared to some official benchmark datasets such as ICDAR series, CocoText, SynthText etc.[12; 13; 14; 15; 16]

Text detection plays a critical role in the procedure of extracting and understanding all text information. The basis of text detection is the design of the features that distinguish the text from the backgrounds.

Many text detection approaches were difficult to perform in challenging scenarios before the field of text learning with deep learning was discovered. Traditional approaches use manually designed[17; 18; 16; 19] features, while deep learning methods learn effective features from training data. These traditional approaches are often multi-stage, and overall performance is slightly less. In this work, three state-of-the-art works will be analyzed for the purpose.: EAST[2], FOTS[5], CRAFT[20].

2.1.1. EAST: AN EFFICIENT AND ACCURATE SCENE TEXT DETECTOR

EAST is a deep learning-based algorithm that detects text with a single neural network with the elimination of multi-stage approaches. The EAST algorithm uses only one neural network to predict a line of text given within the image. It can detect text in arbitrary orientation with quadrilateral shapes. In 2017, this algorithm performed better than cutting-edge methods. This algorithm consists of a fully Convolutional network with a non max suppression (NMS)[21; 22] merging state. Inside the model the Convolutional Neural Network is used to localize text in the image, and this NMS stage is mainly used to combine many imprecise text boxes into one bounding box for each text region (word or line text)

EAST architecture was created taking into account different sizes of word regions. The idea is to identify small word regions that require low-level features from the first stages, while identifying large word regions that require features from the next stage of the neural network. To create this network, the authors used three branches joined together in a single neural network.

Feature Extractor Stem: This stage of the network is used to extract features from different

Figure 1: Structure of EAST text detection

layers of the network. This part can be a pre-trained convolution network on the ImageNet dataset[23] dataset. Authors of EAST architecture used PVANet[24] and VGG16[25] for experiment.

Feature Merging Branch: In this branch of the EAST network, it combines feature outputs from a different layer of the VGG16 network. The input image is passed through the VGG16 model and outputs are obtained from four different VGG16 layers. Combining these feature maps can be computationally expensive, because EAST uses a U-net architecture to progressively combine feature maps, shown in Fig. 1. First, the results from the pool5 layer are sampled upward using a deconvolution layer. Then the size of the properties after this layer will be equal to the output from the pool4 layer and both will be combined in a single layer. Conv 1 X 1 and Conv 3 X 3 are then applied to combine the information and produce the output of this merge step.

Output Layer: The output layer contains a score map and a geometry map, shown in Fig. 2. While the score map shows the probability of text in that region, the geometry map defines the boundary of the text box. This geometry

Geometry	channels	description
AABB	4	$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{R} = \{d_i i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}\}$
RBOX	5	$\mathbf{G} = \{\mathbf{R}, \theta\}$
QUAD	8	$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{Q} = \{(\Delta x_i, \Delta y_i) i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}\}$

Table 1. Output geometry design

Figure 2: Score and Geometry Map Generation. (a) Text quadrangle (yellow dashed) and the shrunk quadrangle (green solid); (b) Text score map; (c) RBOX geometry map generation; (d) 4 channels of distances of each pixel to rectangle boundaries; (e) Rotation angle. This image is taken from[2].

map can be either a rotated box or quadrangle. A rotated box consists of the upper-left coordinate, width, height, and rotation angle for the text box. While quadrangle consists of all four coordinates of a rectangle.

Loss Function: The loss function in [2] is determined as follows:

$$L = L_s + \lambda L_g \quad (1)$$

where L_s and L_g represent the losses for the score map and the geometry, respectively, and λ weighs the importance between two losses. In the EAST paper, authors determined λ as 1.

Non-max Suppression Merging Stage: After the fully Convolutional network, the predicted geometries are passed through a threshold value. After this threshold, the remaining geometries are suppressed using a locality-aware NMS. Naive NMS runs on $O(n^2)$. However, to run it in

$O(n)$, the authors have adopted a method that uses row-by-row suppression. This row-by-row suppression also takes into account the iterative merging of the last merged item. This makes this algorithm fast in most cases, but the worst time complexity is still $O(n^2)$.

2.1.2. FOTS: FAST ORIENTED TEXT SPOTTING WITH A UNIFIED NETWORK

As mentioned earlier, in many models, text detection and recognition are treated as two separate tasks. In the FOTS[5] paper, the authors propose a model capable of detecting and recognizing text simultaneously from the image which means that FOTS is a unified end to end trainable network that uses sharing computation and visual information among the two complementary tasks.

The authors suggest a strategy called shared Convolutional Neural networks, creating a network model that works much faster than two-stage methods. Although this model requires less computation, it learns more common features.

The key point in the FOTS[5] model is to establish the link between detection and recognition parts. The model achieves this connection with the **RoIRotate** technique.

FOTS Network Architecture: The architecture is presented in Fig. 4. Feature maps are firstly extracted with shared convolutions. The fully convolutional network based oriented text detection branch is built on top of the feature map to predict the detection bounding boxes. The RoIRotate operator extracts text proposal features corresponding to the detection results from the feature map. The text proposal features are then pass into Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) encoder and Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC)[26] decoder for text recognition.

RoIRotate: RoIRotate applies transformations on oriented feature regions to obtain axis-aligned feature maps, as shown in Fig. 3. First, it calculates affine parameters with the help of ground truth and predicted coordinates of text propos-

Figure 3: RIO-rotate example. The proposed method uses the input image to illustrate text locations, but it is actually operated on feature maps in the network[5].

als. Then, affine transformations are applied to shared feature maps for each zone and canonical horizontal feature maps are derived from text regions.

Loss Function: In this model, the loss function is calculated by combining the losses from detection and recognition.

$$L = L_{detect} + \lambda L_{recog} \quad (2)$$

λ controls the trade off between recognition and detection loss which is taken 1 by the authors of the paper.

2.1.3. CRAFT: CHARACTER REGION AWARENESS FOR TEXT DETECTION

Unlike EAST and FOTS, the CRAFT model uses character level annotation for text detection training. However, it is difficult to produce and find a dataset annotated on character level.

In the CRAFT paper[20], the authors first propose a solution to the limited character-level dataset problem. Then they come up with a new model for text detection.

Although there is no public character-level dataset available, there are large datasets synthetic as annotated such as SynthText[27]. Using this advantage, the authors propose a model that can make character-level annotation to world-

level annotated datasets like ICDAR datasets[14; 12; 28].

Ground Truth Label Generation: The model in the paper trains synthetic and real images together and produces the **region score** and **affinity score** for word-level annotated boxes. In the paper, authors describe this method as **Weakly-Supervised Learning**. This training is important to extract character level annotation from real pictures. The region score gives the probability that each given pixel belongs to the center of the character and the affinity score represents the center probability of the space between adjacent characters, shown in Fig. 5.

Weakly Supervised Learning: When a real image with word-level annotations is provided, the learned interim model predicts the character region score of the cropped word images to generate character-level bounding boxes, as shown in Fig. 6. Also, the confidence map is calculated by dividing the number of specified characters and the actual character number to ensure the reliability of the model’s prediction. This calculated confidence map is used for weights during training. This training process consists of three stages. First, the world-level annotated boxes are cropped from real images. Second, the model trains until region score prediction. Third, the watershed algorithm[29] is used to separate character compositions.

While training, the CRAFT model can predict characters more accurately. In early training stages, region score can be relatively low. This situation stems from unfamiliar text in natural images. The model learns appearances of new texts, such as irregular fonts, and synthesized texts that have a different data distribution against the SynthText dataset.

The CRAFT model was released in 2019 and has a superior performance compared to previously released models. Results related to the comparison can be learned from the paper[20].

Figure 4: FOTS architecture. The network predicts both text regions and text labels in a single forward pass[5].

Figure 5: Illustration of ground truth generation procedure in the framework. The generated ground truth labels from a synthetic image that has character level annotations. Image taken from [20].

Figure 6: Illustration of the overall training stream for the proposed method. Training is carried out using both real and synthetic images in a weakly-supervised fashion [30].

2.2. Text Recognition

Text recognition and reading capability takes an important place in computer vision tasks. Many practical applications, i.e. hand written texts, tag reading and traffic sign reading requires text recognition. With the development of text detection models[31; 32; 33; 34], text recognition has started to take a very significant place in front of research subjects. Text recognition research is still open and hot topic in computer vision.

Recently, some text recognition methods[35; 36; 37; 38; 39], have achieved significant success. Reading text is naturally considered as multiclassification problem that contains sequence-like objects[38]. These models and methods are usually based on the Convolutional Neural network[40; 9], but also require the integration of Recurrent neural network[41; 38; 32] and attention mechanism[42; 43; 44; 45].

In addition, the text recognition models are generally tested on benchmark datasets such as IIIT5K-Words (IIIT5K)[46], Street View Text (SVT)[47], ICDAR 2003 (IC03)[48], ICDAR 2013 (IC13)[13], SVT-Perspective (SVT-P)[49] and their performance is compared.⁷

Although these models have had great success, various shapes and distorted patterns of the irregular texts give this field a new challenge. Scene texts with irregular shapes, such as perspective and curved texts are still very difficult to recognise, shown in Fig. 7. In the paper "A Multi-Object Rectified Attention Network for Scene Text Recognition"[39] published in 2019 and the authors propose a method for solution to this problem.

2.2.1. MORAN : A MULTI-OBJECT RECTIFIED ATTENTION NETWORK FOR SCENE TEXT RECOGNITION

MORAN[39] is a multi-object rectified attention network that can read curved text, various shapes and stretched characters from different background of images. This model includes two parts, multi-object rectification net-

Figure 7: Example for scene text with irregular shape. [39].

work (MORN) and an attention-based sequence recognition network (ASRN), shown in Fig. 8. While the MORN part is for image rectification, the ASRN part is for reading the text.

Multi-object Rectification Network(MORN): MORN is trained under weak supervision to understand the offset of each part of the image. Rectified text image is produced by predicting the offset. MORN does not predict character categories when predicting position offsets.

The advantages of the MORN method can be summarized as follows:

- MORN gives more readable corrected text resulting in a normal form of the text image with less noise.
- Usually affine transformation methods are used to rectify images, however, these methods are geometrically limited. MORN is more flexible than affine transformation. It has no geometric boundaries and arranges images using complex transformations.
- While the MORN method does not require extra labeling for character positions, it can be trained on existing training data through weak-supervision.

Attention-based Sequence Recognition Network(ASRN): ASRN architecture has attention mechanism with CNN-RNN, shown in Fig. 8. In the model BLSTM stands for bidirectional LSTM[50]. Bidirectional LSTM is a network that consists of two independent RNNs and uses two different inputs at each stage, one from the

Figure 8: MORAN architecture [39].

past and the future. In this way the network preserves information from both past and the other for the future. In the last part of the ASRN, the GRU[51; 52] makes word predictions and the model selects the word with the highest probability

Basically, ASRN decoder learns the relationship between tags and target characters. It is a data-based process and the ability to select the right regions is enhanced by the feedback of correct alignment.

2.2.2. IMAGE-BASED SEQUENCE RECOGNITION AND ITS APPLICATION TO SCENE TEXT RECOGNITION

Text recognition is directly related to image-based sequence recognition. In[38], a neural network architecture is proposed that integrates feature extraction, sequence modeling and transcription into a unified framework. The advantages of the model proposed in this paper can be listed as follows:

- The network can be trained end to end, unlike most existing algorithms whose components are individually trained and tuned.
- It processes sequences naturally from random lengths, without characters segmentation or horizontal scale normalization.
- The model is effective and small, which is more practical for real application scenarios.

Figure 9: The network architecture[38].

The CRNN model proposed in the article consists of three parts, shown in Fig. 9. These are Convolutional layers, the Recurrent layers and transcription layer parts. While the Convolutional layer part extracts features from each given image, the Recurrent Neural Network part makes predictions for each frame. The transaction layer in the last part converts the prediction made for each frame into a label sequence. As a result, CRNN[38] is formed by training CNN and RNN together with a single loss function.

Feature Sequence Extraction: In this part, a sequence of feature vectors is extracted from fea-

Figure 10: The receptive field. Each vector in the extracted feature sequence is associated with a receptive field on the input image, and can be considered as the feature vector of that field [38].

ture maps produced by the Convolutional layers component. Each feature vector array is created by generating a feature, from left to right, on feature maps. Each column on the feature map is associated with a rectangle on the original image, and the rectangular regions (receptive field) are in the same row from left to right, shown in Fig. 10.

Sequence Labeling: This part is created by combining bidirectional Recurrent neural Networks, thus predicting label distribution for each frame in the feature sequence.

Transcription: Transformation of RNN predictions into label-sequences for each frame is a process of finding a transcription. In other words transcription is a process of finding the highest probability label sequence which is conditioned on the per-frame predictions. Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC)[26] is used to calculate the loss function based on that conditional probability. Experiments on benchmark datasets have been observed that the CRNN model proposed in the article gives better results than other CNN and RNN based models[53; 9].

3. Methodology

To develop an Optical Character Recognition system that can read traffic signs with high performance, firstly the analyzed models should be tested and compared with the proposed model.

Therefore, in this research, a special dataset consisting of real traffic signs was prepared and tested with past models and the proposed model.

Mapillary is the street-level imagery platform that scales and automates mapping using collaboration, cameras, and computer vision. Contributors of the Mapillary want to represent the whole world with photos. Mapillary connects to the OpenStreetMap platform that everyone can contribute and upload images from all around the world.

Traffic sign recognition is one of the crucial subjects that matters for autonomous driving and smart cities. By using the advantage of computer vision algorithm that detects traffic signs and classify automatically from street level images, Mapillary extracted traffic signs[54] and introduced the worlds largest and most diverse traffic sign dataset.

Therefore, when preparing data sets, The OpenStreetMap platform offered by Mapillary was used.

3.1. Datasets

First, 5 different regions were selected from United: Los Angeles, Austin, Washington, Hayward and Detroit. As mentioned earlier, Mapillary has already computer vision algorithm that detects traffic signs and classify from street view with its map features.

The traffic signs belonging to the classes containing text from the traffic sign objects in the regions were selected by using Mapillary API. Then the images were downloaded in those areas where these objects were visible. Then, using the keys of the images that were downloaded, the traffic sign coordinates were determined in each image. Finally, those coordinates were cropped from each image, shown in Fig. 11.

In this way, different numbers of traffic signs containing text for each region were obtained.

At this point we have labelled them manually according to the quality of the photos and the text they contain.

Collecting the datasets

Traffic sign extraction using mapillary object detections. Scope: US parking signs.

Figure 11: Example from the street view of traffic signs.

For the quality of traffic sign we determined three classes as high, ok and low, shown in Fig. 12.

Many OCR systems as described in the relative work section were divided into two parts. One is detection of the text spot and the other one is text recognition. Therefore, two different training data sets are needed, one for detection and the other for recognition.

3.1.1. TEXT SPOTTING TRAIN DATASET

To be able to train with OCR models, bounding box coordinates containing text in images provided as input must be known, and what is written in it. But in real life it is hard to annotate thousands of images. However, this problem can be solved by preparing a synthetic data set.

Two types of data sets were prepared for text perception training.

The initial training data includes a total of 600 actual traffic signs, and these traffic signs were taken from the Chicago area, shown in Fig. 13.

Second, an annotation was added to around 200 traffic sign templates to create a synthetic dataset. It is essential to simulate real traffic signs to create a synthetic dataset.

Each image was rotated in 9 different angles [5,10, ..., 45] both right and left.

After the traffic signs were rotated, the changing corners of the boxes were calculated. Boxes were recalculated using the formula below:

$$X = x \times \cos \theta - y \times \sin \theta \quad (3)$$

$$Y = x \times \sin \theta + y \times \cos \theta \quad (4)$$

Additionally, cropped images from real street images were added to the background of rotated synthetic signs and also random blur was added, shown in Fig. 14

In this way, 7000 synthetic datasets were created for text detection training.

3.1.2. TEXT RECOGNITION TRAIN DATASET

For text recognition training data, only need small images with short text groups. Therefore, half of the text recognition model's training data was taken from actual traffic signs that were annotated manually. Bounding box coordinates containing already annotated text from actual traffic signs, shown in Fig. 15 are truncated.

The other half of the recognition data set was synthetically created by using TextRecognitionDataGenerator[55] tool.

OCR FOR PARKING SIGNS

Region	Low quality	Ok quality	High quality	Unique Signs	Total detections
Los Angeles	1132	575	531	583	2240
Austin	689	456	612	692	1842
Detroit	753	546	518	756	1821
Hayward	2086	753	1213	993	4055
Washington	1535	536	780	884	2851

Figure 12: Parking sign benchmark dataset statistics.

34, 17, 3, 21, 7, 51, 38, 47, NO
 77, 43, 7, 56, 12, 83, 82, 70, STOPPING
 43, 80, 18, 84, 21, 104, 47, 99, ANY
 73, 73, 47, 77, 50, 97, 76, 94, TIME

Figure 13: Example for annotation of real traffic sign crop.

Figure 16: Examples from synthetic Text Recognition Dataset

Figure 14: Synthetic dataset generation

Figure 15: Real Text Recognition Datasetn

In U.S.A. traffic signs have usually different versions of Highway Gothic fonts. In addition, a dictionary of words that can be included in traffic signs has been prepared. Synthetic recognition data was generated using this dictionary and 5 different Highway-Gothic fonts[56] in that tool[55], shown in Fig. 16

3.2. Proposed method

Text Detection Part: We found the FOTS[5] model suitable for the detection part because the FOTS model has better performance than the EAST[2] model and also it only requires word-level bounding box labelled data. In fact, when looking at the reviews in the papers, it will be seen that, the CRAFT[20] model works better than FOTS, but the CRAFT model needs character-level annotation or needs to be trained weakly-supervised with SynthText[27] dataset which needs a lot of computational power. Also, there is no big difference between the results of the FOTS model and the CRAFT model. Papers can be examined for detailed results[5; 20].

This[57] application was used to train the tagged parking sign dataset built with the FOTS model. However, as can be expected, this implementation was made for ICDAR 2015[12] dataset, so some modifications had been made.

First the long portions of the pictures were fixed at 768 pixels and short pieces were enlarged in the same proportion. Then the pictures are rotated between [-5.5] at random. When rescaling the height of the images from 0.5 to 3.0 were left unchanged in width. After that, a random sample of 192x192 was taken from transformed images.

While the FOTS model was being trained, it was used as a bottleneck for ResNet-50 features for parking sign pictures.

While the data training was in progress, RIO thresholding was applied and the NMS method was applied to the predicted boxes. These predicted boxes were given to the recognition section to get the recognition results. For multi-scale testing, all results scales are combined and sent back to NMS to get the final results.

Text Recognition Part: We were inspired by the study in[38] paper for the text recognition part of the parking sign OCR system that we were trying to create. The reason we chose [38] was that it works very efficiently, and it is easy to implement. So the creation of our model include three basic parts, as described in the paper. The model consists of a combination of Convolutional Neural network[58], Recurrent Neural network[44] and Connectionist Temporal Classification[26] loss.

$$MODEL = CNN + RNN + CTC_{loss} \quad (5)$$

As a result, the model consists of three different parts:

1. Convolutional Neural Network part helps to extract features from images.
2. Recurrent neural network part in order to predict sequential output per time step.

3. Connectionist Temporal Classification(CTC) loss function, the transcription layer used to predict the output for each time step.

The following ways were followed while creating the architecture:

1. In the architecture created, the height of the input images was determined as 32 and the width as 128..
2. Seven convolution layers were used of which 6 are having kernel size (3,3) and the last one is of size (2,2). And the number of filters is increased from 64 to 512 layer by layer.
3. Two max-pooling layers are added with size (2,2) and then two max-pooling layers of size (2,1) are added to extract features with a larger width to predict long texts.
4. The batch normalization also added to layers after the fifth and sixth layers of convolution that speeded up the training process.
5. Next, lambda function used to squeeze the output from the Convolutional layer and make it compatible with the LSTM layer.
6. Then, two bidirectional LSTM layers with 128 units each were used. This RNN layer outputs the dimension (batch-size, 31, 63). 63 is the total number of output classes, including null characters.

Loss of Connectionist Temporal Classification(CTC)[26] is very helpful in text recognition problems. It helps to avoid adding notes at any time step and avoids the problem that a single character can span multiple times, which requires more processing without usage of CTC.

A CTC loss function requires four arguments to calculate the loss, predicted outputs, ground truth labels, the sequence length of the LSTM, and the ground truth label length. To achieve this, a special loss function must be created and

Figure 17: Schematic representation of parking sign OCR

added to this model. To combine it with the model, a model was created that takes these four inputs and subtracts the loss.

The schematic visual of the system created can be examined, shown in Fig. 17.

4. Experimental results and discussions

4.1. Evaluation Methods and Evaluated Models

Two different terminologies were determined while evaluating the results. Recall and Precision defined to evaluate OCR results:

C.T. (correct text): the number of signs which read as correct.

- **Recall:** The number of signs for which an OCR result was returned.
- **Precision:** $\frac{C.T.}{Recall}$

Recall was defined as the number of signs for which an OCR result was returned. In other words, If the OCR system returns text from a photo given to it, then the recall increased with one.

The Precision defined as a rate which shows us the percentage of correct texts from the returned texts on a given OCR systems.

Levenshtein and Generalized Jaccard similarity used to determine if a returning text is correct or not.

The Levenshtein distance is a string metric for measuring the difference between two sequences. Informally, the Levenshtein distance[83, 84, 85, 86] between two words is the minimum number of single-character edits (insertions, deletions or substitutions) required to change one word into the other. In evaluations Levenshtein similarity measure was used, representing the normalized levenshtein similarity score between two strings. For example, to convert the word "sample" to "examples", 3 adjustments are required and the last word as "example" contains 7 letters, then the levenshtein similarity is calculated as $1 - 3/7 = 0.57$.

The jaccard similarity for two sets is intersection of two sets divided by two sets. For instance the set ["data", "science"] and ["data", "management"] has 1 element in their intersection and 3 elements in the union therefore the jaccard similarity between two sets are $1/3=0.33333$

- **Jaccard (X,Y) :** $\frac{|X \cap Y|}{|X \cup Y|}$

Generalized Jaccard similarity measure is soft-ened version of the Jaccard measure. The Jaccard measure is promising candidate for tokens which exactly match across the sets. However, in practice tokens are often misspelled, such as energy vs. The generalized Jaccard measure will enable matching in such cases. Jaro similarity and threshold used inside the Generalized Jaccard function.

The Jaro Similarity is calculated using the following formula:

- **Jaro Similarity:**

$$\begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } m = 0 \\ \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{m}{|s_1|} + \frac{m}{|s_2|} + \frac{m-t}{m} \right), & \text{for } \end{cases}$$

where;

- **m** is the number of matching characters
- **t** is half the number of transpositions
- where $|s_1|$ and $|s_2|$ is the length of strings s_1 and s_2

Characters are matching;

- if they are same,

and;

- the characters are not farther than,

$$\left\lfloor \frac{\max(|s_1|, |s_2|)}{2} \right\rfloor$$

Therefore, the Generalized Similarity function has two parameters one is similarity function which is determined as jaro and threshold value. If the similarity of a token pair exceeds the threshold, then the token pair is considered a match.

Therefore, in order to evaluate OCR results, these two measures of similarity were used as Generalized Jaccard and levenshtein.

Threshold values were determined for each similarity:

- Levensthein similarity treshold : **0.75**
- Generalized Jaccard similarity treshold : **0.80**

As a result, if text returned from the OCR system exceeds these thresholds compared to the actual text then marked correctly labelled. In order to evaluate the results in more detail and to

better understand and analyze the proposed system, each category were evaluated (image quality as low, ok, high) separately.

In addition, the photos with a resolution greater than 100 x 70 were evaluated in a separate plot and the images where the traffic signs were detected at the best resolution.

Resolution analysis were also made for each region separately

Pretrained text detection and text recognition methods were used from different systems to evaluate the results.

The results of 9 different systems were used and these are;

- **Google:** The Google Cloud Vision API used directly to review the text results from Google's OCR system. One can get the JSON file that includes the entire extracted string, as well as individual words, and their bounding boxes from images by sending the images to the API as base64 encoded string. For more information, see the Google documentation.[59]
- **Amazon:** The Amazon Rekognition API used for this operation. It has similar logic with Google Cloud Vision API. To use this engine, it must be provided as base64-encoded byte-sequence photos or as an image stored in an Amazon S3. This engine returns JSON file that includes the following items:
 - The detected text (DetectedText).
 - The location of text on the image (Geometry).
 - The confidence Amazon Rekognition has in the accuracy of the detected text and bounding box (Confidence).
 - The type of the detected text (Type).

For more information, see the documentation.[60].

- **Tesseract:** Tesseract is a text recognition engine offered by Google as a free software since 2006. It is working on different operating systems (Windows, Linux etc.). Tesseract supports a wide variety of languages. It is an open source software that can directly download and use for recognition. For more information, see the Tesseract documentation[61].

- **Tesseract-det:** Tesseract is normally for reading text inline, so it gives much better results if used with a text detector. Because, in order for the tesseract to be feed, the text field should be determined from any image and then cut and give to the tesseract.

For this reason, a pre-trained model was taken with the EAST (An Efficient and Accurate Scene Text Detector)[62] model previously trained on ICDAR 2013 (training set) + ICDAR 2015 (training set), and the results were analyzed by combining it with tesseract.

- **Tesseract-craft:** The same method described and used above was used. However, this time, CRAFT-trained[20] model was used instead of EAST model.
- **Fots-tesseract :** The FOTS model was trained using previously created synthetic and real traffic sign data sets. Later, the detection part of the FOTS model was combined with the tesseract.
- **Fots-moran :** The detection part of the FOTS model was used again, but this time pre-trained MORAN (A Multi-Object Rectified Attention Network for Scene Text Recognition)[63] in the text recognition section was used.
- **Fots-our :** Here, the FOTS cite 8578693 detection model used above was used. However, this time proposed text recognition model was trained with the previously created text recognition data set. While creating the model, the article "End-to-End Trainable Neural Network and Scene Text

Recognition Application for Image Based Sequence Recognition" was used.[38].

- **Fots-our-new :** This part is actually not much different from Fots, which is the model described above, only some problems in the system were analyzed and some improvements were added.

4.2. Training Process

Separate trainings were held for the text detection and recognition sections. FOTS[5] model was used for detection training. An End-to-End Trainable Neural Network for Image-based Sequence Recognition and Its Application to Scene Text Recognition model used for recognition training.

For text detection training, FOTS model used implemented in PyTorch. 10% of the dataset allocated for validation. used Res-Net50 features used as a backbone to trained images. One Tesla P100 used GPU for training and it took 20 hours for 40 epochs also the batch size as 96 with learning rate 0.0001 and Adam optimizer. Checkpoints were recorded for each epoch and then used for evaluation of the results.

Data augmentation is important for robustness of deep neural networks, especially when the number of real data is limited, as in this case.

For this reason, it was tried to increase the data set prepared for recognition training with a certain logic. Firstly, the width of each recognition photo was fixed to 32 and the height of each photo was changed in the same proportion. Four different methods were used to resize each photograph, including nearest neighbor interpolation, double linear interpolation, resampling using pixel area relationship, and two cubic interpolations over a 4 X 4 pixel neighborhood. These methods were used as OpenCV from the python library. For more information, see the documentation[64]. Then, using these four methods, each photo was reduced at 12 different rates. Because in real traffic sign samples, the size of the image obtained when the text area

is cut after detection can be very different. So, such a path was taken to simulate this situation.

Before starting Recognition training, preprocess has been done to input images and labels. Each image read and convert into a gray-scale image, and make each image of size (128,32) by using padding. Then image dimension was expanded as (128,32,1) to make it compatible with the input shape of architecture. Finally, normalization was also made with the image pixel values by dividing it with 255. To preprocess the output, labels were encoded each character of a word into some numerical value by creating a function(as 'a':0, 'b':1 'z':26 etc). Let say we are having the word 'abab' then the encoded label would be [0,1,0,1].

Two other lists were created as one is label length and other is input length to RNN(Recurrent Neural Network). These two lists are important for CTC(Connectionist Temporal Classification) loss.

10% of the dataset prepared for validation was reserved for validation, which means training on 240 128 samples and validation on 26680 samples.

After all these preprocess, the text recognition model was trained with 50 epochs and 256 batch size on one tesla P100 GPU.

Adam optimizer used with a learning rate of 0.001. After each epoch saved the weights of the best model on the basis of validation loss.

4.3. Results

There are 6 different parcels for 5 different regions. Hayward's results are shared here, but other results can be checked from appendix, A.

First, all traffic sign images of the Hayward area were evaluated, shown in Fig. 18.

In addition, the recall results were evaluated separately from all Hayward traffic sign detections, shown in Fig. 19.

When the results are examined, it turns out that the system can find a detection box for al-

Figure 18: Precision Scores from all Hayward traffic sign detections

Figure 19: Recall scores from Hayward Region

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Figure 20: The number of the correctly classified texts

most every traffic sign, but either the recognition part cannot read the bounding boxes or some of the bounding boxes returned from the system are turning completely wrong.

In order to better understand this situation, it is useful to examine the numbers that appear directly, shown in Fig. 20. Looking at the correct classified text numbers, it appears that more text than Google is classified correctly. However, because of the high recall the precision appears lower.

If only the high resolution images of the Hayward region are taken into account, it is seen that the precision scores of the system are almost at the level of Google, shown in Fig. 21. On the other hand, if the recall scores are examined, it is seen that they are at the same level as Google, shown in Fig. 22 This shows that there is only a slight difference between the proposed system and Google s results, but Google s results are still better.

If only ok quality images are taking into account and analyzed, It appears to be less between Google and the recommended system, shown in Fig. 23,24.

On the other hand, when only low quality images are examined, the recommended system works much better(according to Levenshtein metric), shown in Fig. 25,26. This special case can be explained as follows: Normally, while Google producing OCR results, if the photo

Figure 21: Results of high-quality photos of the Hayward region

Figure 22: Recall of high-quality images of the Hayward region

Figure 23: Results of ok-quality photos of the Hayward region

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Figure 24: Recall of ok-quality photos of the Hayward region

Figure 26: Recall of low-quality photos of the Hayward region

Figure 25: Results of low-quality photos of the Hayward region

Figure 27: Precision scores for resolution greater than 100px

quality is very low, it does not return text because it is not sure about the box containing the text (Low Confidence Level). However, since the proposed system is only trained on traffic signs, it tries to find boxes that contain text even in very low quality photographs and at least a certain part of it is correct. Besides, the proposed recognition system that have trained can read even in difficult situations, especially since it sees even very low quality writing sets beforehand.

Finally, it was analyzed using only traffic sign photos with a resolution greater than 100 pixels, shown in Fig. 27,28.

As can be seen from the qualitative results, the proposed system is generally better than Google at low quality photos. It is important and good

Figure 28: Recall scores for resolution greater than 100px

and there is still room for improvement of the system and in difficult situations it can already do better than Google. in their awesome family and navigated me at all aspects of my internship and master thesis.

5. Conclusion

In the present study, a benchmark dataset representative was identified to understand parking signs. In addition, a special OCR system for parking signs has been proposed. The proposed model outperformed open source methodologies like a tesseract. It reaches an equal or better performance than commercial cloud-based systems(Google, Amazon, etc.) on this task. The system produced worked especially well with very low-quality images, which is the more difficult case for OCR systems. There are many aspects that need to be improved. This study shows and proves that instead of general trained OCR systems, systems designed and developed for special use-cases can be created, and they can work much better than general systems.

As future work, real data annotation can be increased and more the realistic synthetic dataset can be developed. Because of the limited real dataset, the system could not understand some special cases very well and the synthetic dataset was not enough to simulate the real dataset. For example, by adding things like shadow, special noise, perspective transform in a synthetic dataset, a more realistic simulation can be created.

In addition, by using a different and special data augmentation method the Neural Network can get a sufficient boost in detection and recognition abilities.

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Appendix A. Appendix